

Human
Illusory Sense
of
Freewill

By

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Sense Of Distinctness: Existence

Life is the swift impact of latent and palpable manifestations, and the initial action or reaction of the entity to these latent and observable manifestations: and living is the experiences acquired and the extent to which the entity adapts to the modulating and modifying effect of these experiences, and the extent to which the entity by itself tweaks and relays the experiences. Nonetheless, the sense of existence isn't configured for consciousness of which existence is an offshoot of. But the sense of existence is configured for the discernment of the varying senses of existence that are performing varying complementary functions.

Like life and living, existence (sense of distinctness) is spasmodic whereas Being is invincibly limitless.

Although, consciousness is understanding of wave pattern and the direction of latent and observable occurrences, it is analogous to being. However, Existence, which is (in relation to human) the absolute extent of human-perception of infinite possibilities, or the extent to which observable possibilities affect the senses, is a saturation on consciousness. Thus, an entity distinctness and its sense of existence are structured by varying effect of latent and observable manifestations that are post consciousness quantization.

Root Of Human Sense Of Will

Reality is intensely highly less phenomenological. It is the correlation of the nonphysical with the physical; the invincible influence of nonphysical on perceptions and the coordination of possibilities and certainties by time. Hence, the nonphysical can be relatively described as the recessive point on the scale of perception whereas objectively, the nonphysical (Nothing) is Everything and the source of human and, of human inventions.

The human form is a tool for processing Nothing. When thoughts or mind is in sync with hands, humans knit Nothing into existence. Nothing is 'infinitesimally latent' and infinitely imponderable possibilities, outcomes and occurrences of which the mind is a fragment. Hence, the mind within its frame of existence is a repository of random innumerable possibilities.

There are defined response accompaniment to varying level of energy frequencies which human is a peculiar form. And as a processor, human don't exercise freewill. Life is osmotic and palpable thus stimulating associate response. These are embeddedly encrypted and imponderable responses with adaptive recursive reflexes that are varyingly decrypted through sublime random symbiotic relation between entities and ambience. It shows that actions and reactions are responses to latent and adaptively permeating experiences that are pre-produced. Therefore, one can conclude that human sense of free-will is delusive.

The mechanism for the illusory sense of free-will is time coordinated low recessive and saturating repercussion of post-recursive reflexes. Like all other forms, the human form transduces; transceives, adopts, adapts and has symbiotic capacitance. The only difference is that these forms respond to, and relay their subliminal experiences varyingly. Humans gain the ability to make seeming independent decision from experiences while time determines choices. Hence, the human ability to think, conceive, synthesize ideas and assimilate them into everyday life only prove that the human form is an 'efficient tool', doesn't mean that the form gives the ability to make independent decisions.

Function And Effect Of Time On Freewill

Omning Time is the instant of perception and the destructive instant of reverberated perception while Formal Time is a resonant constriction that subliminally effects and modulates its relative source and the latently inducted collective.

Root of Disagreement And Agreement

Belief isn't necessary grounded on truth, which is a verifiably relayed information or a statement that is dependent on trust, which is only subsequent to knowing of which is the capability to replicate an idea. Belief is a measurably irrational hypnotic approbation that stem from an intermediary preposition. Whereupon, no one really disagrees with, because of observable inconsistencies. And physical evidence is no guarantee that an agreement will be reached. Because attraction, repulsion: agreement and disagreement are all determined by the type of bond between persons. Fundamentally, agreement and disagreement are determined by measurable crave, which is a thing that a person is auto-suggestively addicted to which isn't really determined by time variation, though its influence is occasionally vitiated by time variation. Agreement and disagreement are also determined by the correlation between a messenger, a receiver and the vehicle for an idea. In addition, the degree to which an idea or a doctrine is accepted, is determined solely by the intensity of the subliminal effect of its vehicle ($\text{Material-Effect} \sim 4 + y + x$) and the components of its configuration in relation to position. Thus, the act of disagreeing with or to, is triggered by an auto-suggestive retraction from a latently subliminal dissonance that stems from certain polarity between attractions, the effect of time oscillation and its resultant modulating effect on human perception rate; whereas an agreement with any form of thought is initiated by a subliminal attraction that is so often determined by time.

Furthermore, human has pre-configured primary disposition; and acquire adaptive and alternately superimposing disposition that is structured by adoptable variable that modulates and makes human primary attributes highly susceptible to time oscillation. Thus making time the major cause of humans' sudden and highly observably behavioural change. Time alternates humans' modulated and modified perceptions by regulating human disposition in relation to varying attractions and positions. And like human inconsistent relationship, the relationship between nations oscillate between diplomacy and aggression. As a result, conflict nor war isn't caused by collision of polarized intent but rather, by Time-Triggered-Inclination: time is the catalysts that trigger fight between people, precipitates nation into insurrection; and countries into wars.

Options and Choice

Life balance is pivoted on the ratio of possibilities to certainties' frequencies and life annihilation is directly proportional to simultaneous certainties. As a result, action, reaction, attraction, repulsion and the resultant responses and relationship are inertia until acted upon by time. And the impact level of activities are directly proportional to the catalysts' exclusive and complementary variables harmony with position and time. And because possibilities and certainties' are governed by time, the nine variation on set of possibilities aren't presented annually. Time only presents four varying set of possibilities annually, and each is made up of innumerably parallel and random options, which are either Static: a set of four variable options that are congruent with a person's position or Dynamic: a set of four variable options that time has shuffled, and presented a person with as annual options that are in sync with time but all options may not be congruent with a person's position.

In addition, the susceptible law states that an observer perception of an entity (i.e. person) is determined by a subliminal relation between the observer and the person and the attributes of the person in relation to position and time. Or the actions, reactions and responses of entities A and B have subliminal effect on their observer, and the judgment of the observer is determined by the respective configurations of A and B and the degree to which A and B attract their observer. Hence, the certainty that any option will influence a picker and that the picker will show preference for, and make any choice is also determined by the degree of the pickers complementary variables harmony with the option's augment, position and time.